

1 **Title**

2 Heat-related mortality in Europe during 2023 and the role of adaptation in protecting health

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34 **Abstract**

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36 The year of 2023 was the warmest on record globally, and second warmest in Europe. Here we applied
37 epidemiological models to temperature and mortality records in 823 contiguous regions from 35 countries to estimate
38 sex- and age-specific heat-related mortality in Europe during 2023, and quantify the mortality burden avoided by
39 societal adaptation to rising temperatures since the year 2000. We estimated 47,690 (95% CI = 28,853-66,525) heat-
40 related deaths in 2023, the second highest mortality burden during the study period 2015-2023, only surpassed by
41 2022. We also estimated that the heat-related mortality burden would have been +80.0% higher in absence of present-
42 century adaptation, especially in the elderly (+100.7% in people aged 80+ years). Our results highlight the importance
43 of historical and ongoing adaptations in saving lives during recent summers, and the urgency for more effective
44 strategies to further reduce the mortality burden of forthcoming hotter summers.

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48 **Main**

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50 Anthropogenic climate change is having an increasing impact on the lives and health of billions of people around
51 the world^{1,2}. The year of 2023 was the hottest on record³, fueled by heat-trapping greenhouse gases and a naturally
52 occurring El Niño event⁴, with nearly half of the days exceeding the 1.5°C threshold established in the Paris
53 Agreement⁵. Staying within this threshold is key to minimize the health risks and impacts and the need for further
54 adaptation⁶. However, multi-annual climate forecasts indicate that this limit is likely to be exceeded before the year
55 2027⁷.

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57 Within this context, Europe is warming at a rate twice as fast as the global average⁸, with increasing health impacts
58 due to summer heat that challenge the resilience of European societies and public health systems⁹⁻¹¹. In 2003, several
59 European countries failed to cope with the health consequences of an exceptionally warm summer, with over 70,000
60 excess deaths reported¹². The event raised awareness on the health effects of summer temperatures, triggering a wave

61 of heat prevention plans, including preparedness and response strategies, intervention actions and heat-health early
62 warning systems¹³⁻¹⁵, but their degree of effectiveness is still highly uncertain¹⁶.

63

64 Almost two decades later, over 60,000 heat-related deaths were associated with the record-breaking summer
65 temperatures of 2022 in Europe^{17,18}. The comparable magnitude of the death toll during the summers 2003 and 2022
66 raised doubts about the role of adaptation in preventing deaths, and what would have been the mortality burden in
67 recent years without the effect of temporal changes in the vulnerability to heat. To address this question, here we
68 quantified the heat-related mortality burden during the year of 2023, computed for weeks warmer than the minimum
69 mortality temperature, and fitted epidemiological models in factual-counterfactual scenarios (Figures 1a,b) to
70 measure the role of adaptation in containing the death toll of 2023 in a context of rising temperatures. In the present
71 study, for the sake of convenience, we defined adaptation as any temporal change in the exposure-response
72 associations, both including the minimum mortality temperature and the relative risks.

73

74 We used temperature and mortality records in 823 contiguous regions from 35 countries, representing a population
75 of 543 million Europeans, to fit epidemiological models for the pre-pandemic period 2015-2019, and in this way,
76 estimate the sex- and age-specific heat-related mortality in 2023. We estimated 47,690 (95% CI = 28,853-66,525) heat-
77 related deaths in Europe during the year of 2023 (Table 1), of which 47,312 (95% CI = 28,663-65,998) deaths were
78 estimated to occur between May 29th and October 1st (Extended Data Figure 1). Sensitivity analyses showed little
79 sensitivity to the main parameter choices (Supplementary Table 1). This mortality burden represents the second
80 highest annual value in the study period 2015-2023, only after 2022¹⁷. The highest overall heat-related mortality rates
81 were found in Southern Europe (Figure 1c), especially in Greece (393 deaths per million, 95% CI = 298-483), Bulgaria
82 (229, 95% CI = 123-343), Italy (209, 95% CI = 155-265), Spain (175, 95% CI = 114-238), Cyprus (167, 95% CI = 50-263)
83 and Portugal (136, 95% CI = 92-178; Extended Data Table 1). We note that these countries have already been shown
84 to have an elevated vulnerability to heat in previous years and periods^{10,17,19}. Results stratified by sex and age showed
85 higher heat-related mortality rates in women (women-to-men ratio = 1.55) and the elderly (ratio between 80+ and 65-
86 79 years equal to 8.68), both overall in Europe and in the majority of regions (Figures 1d-f) and countries (Extended
87 Data Tables 1, 2).

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89 There were four major extreme heat and high mortality episodes during the summer of 2023 (Extended Data Figure
90 1). The temporal evolution of these events was markedly different from the one observed during the summer of 2022,
91 when the occurrence of very warm and persistent temperature anomalies during the central part of the summer
92 exacerbated the death toll from mid-July to mid-August, leading to almost two-third of the overall summer heat-
93 related mortality burden of 2022¹⁷. In 2023, no major warm anomalies were registered during these critical central
94 weeks, with 57.5% (27,428 deaths, 95% CI = 18,741-36,588) of the overall annual heat-related mortality attributable to
95 two episodes in mid-July and late August. We estimated 13,021 (95% CI = 9,136-17,098) heat-related deaths during
96 weeks 28-29 (between July 10th and 23rd), with high mortality in Southern European countries and, to a lesser extent,
97 in Germany. On the other hand, 14,407 (95% CI = 9,605-19,490) heat-related deaths were estimated during weeks 33-
98 34 (between August 14th and 27th), not only in these same countries, but also in regions at higher latitudes such as in
99 the Baltic countries.

100

101 We additionally estimated the heat-related mortality in 2023 that was prevented by temporal changes in the
102 cumulative exposure-response association occurred since the year 2000, which are generally interpreted as the result
103 of general socioeconomic progress and specific climate change adaptation measures^{20,21}. Towards this aim, we
104 separately fitted epidemiological models with data from the periods 2000-2004, 2005-2009, 2010-2014 and 2015-2019
105 in the 429 regions from the 23 European countries for which data were available (find the overall association for the
106 ensemble of regions in Figures 1a,b). The different fittings have been subsequently used to transform the temperature
107 and mortality timeseries of 2023 into estimates of heat related mortality during 2023. In this way, it was possible to
108 estimate the mortality numbers and rates that would have been associated to heat if the temperatures of 2023 had
109 been recorded in previous historical periods, according to the different levels of societal and human vulnerability to
110 heat of European regions in previous historical periods (see Methods).

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112 We generally estimated monotonically increasing heat-related mortality numbers and rates in all sex and age
113 categories as we fitted models with data from progressively older periods. For example, if the temperatures of 2023
114 had occurred during the period 2000-2004, the impact of heat on mortality would have been +80.0% higher in the
115 general population, compared to the reference period 2015-2019 (Table 1). We estimated similar increases for women
116 (+83.1%) and men (+86.0%), but largely different increases for people aged 0-64 (+62.5%), 65-79 (+78.6%) and 80+

117 (+100.7%) years. Changes were relatively constant over time, although we found generally sharper transitions
118 between the periods 2005-2009 and 2010-2014.

119
120 All these differences between factual and counterfactual models arose from temporal changes in the epidemiological
121 associations, mainly in the minimum mortality temperature, which progressively warmed in the general population
122 by +2.7°C between 2000-2004 (15.0°C) and 2015-2019 (17.7°C, Table 1). While this is an indication of adaptation to
123 moderate hot temperatures, the relative risk calculated at high temperature centiles has remained stable or slightly
124 increased (Table 1, Figures 1a,b), showing that there may be limits to ongoing adaptation which are not yet
125 completely established and understood.^{22,23} An increase in the minimum mortality temperature along the first two
126 decades of the 21st century has already been observed in some countries, with a subsequent decrease in heat-related
127 mortality^{21,24,25}.

128
129 Our results showed how present-century adaptation has substantially reduced heat-related mortality burden of the
130 summer of 2023, especially in the elderly. This finding suggests improvements in individual behaviors and public
131 health measures reaching the most vulnerable populations. These results were however calculated from a subset of
132 23 countries, highlighting once more, the need for more complete open-access datasets representing the whole
133 continent and time period. Nonetheless, if we speculatively assumed that the same percentage changes in
134 temperature-related mortality had occurred in the ensemble of 35 countries, we would obtain a counterfactual
135 mortality burden for the year of 2023 of 85,842 (95% CI = 51,935-119,745) heat-related deaths with the epidemiological
136 association of the period 2000-2004. This number largely exceeds the 70,000 excess deaths registered during the
137 record-breaking episode of 2003¹², which is a reminder of the generally warmer temperatures in the present decade.
138 The magnitude of the counterfactual mortality burden highlights the urgent need for better and more exhaustive
139 monitoring of climate change impacts on vulnerable populations, with more ambitious and effective prevention
140 plans to achieve an effective early adaptation to climate change²⁶. Although European public institutions should
141 address the problem of high-quality, open-access data in Europe, ongoing initiatives are in place to overcome data
142 access limitations, and provide more precise estimates in the continent²⁷.

143

144 We analyzed the effect of outdoor temperatures, which are generally used for health impact studies analyzing
145 adaptation trends, or for public health actions such as early warning systems and heat action plans. Instead, the effect
146 of indoor temperatures is beyond the scope of the study, given that it has rather mechanistic aims offering other
147 kinds of valuable insights. When we evaluate the adaptation over the century, we quantify the heat-related mortality
148 that would have been estimated if the outdoor temperatures of 2023 had occurred in previous historical periods
149 according to the corresponding levels of vulnerability to heat of European societies. The adaptation that we estimate
150 implicitly includes a broad range of factors encompassing infrastructure, technological and behavioral adaptation.
151 An evaluation of how the indoor conditions have changed is indeed implied, but it is not the only factor here
152 evaluated, and it cannot be extrapolated from our analyses.

153
154 The study has some limitations worth acknowledging. We only analyzed all-cause mortality because cause-specific
155 mortality data were not available. It would indeed be worth it to analyze the regional differences and temporal trends
156 in heat-related vulnerability and mortality among sex and age groups as part of a wider examination of their causes
157 of disease. Moreover, the use of weekly temperatures is expected to underestimate the heat-related mortality of 2023.
158 Our previous study¹⁸ used a daily temperature and mortality database for a large ensemble of European regions to
159 show that weekly data can be used to approximate the heat-related mortality burden obtained from daily data
160 models. Although this result has been considered as a boon for health adaptation in low-resource settings²⁸, weekly
161 data are still today the only available option to estimate the mortality burden in a high-income continent like Europe.
162 We analyzed differences between estimates in daily and weekly data models to develop a methodology to bias-
163 correct the estimations obtained from the weekly data model. We applied this technique to the results of the present
164 study, and found that the resulting heat-related mortality in 2023 (58,139 deaths, 95% CI = 35,175-81,101) was only
165 about 20% smaller than the bias-corrected estimate for 2022¹⁸. Refined methodological techniques are urgently
166 required to provide unbiased and more precise estimates of the mortality burden with currently available data and
167 resources.

168
169 The present work showed that the heat-related mortality during the summer of 2023 was the second highest during
170 the study period 2015-2023, only surpassed by 2022, and that present-century adaptation played a crucial role in
171 preventing a much larger heat-related mortality burden. Heat prevention plans were generally developed and

172 implemented in European countries during this period, especially after the summer of 2003. It is still unclear the
173 relative contribution of these plans as compared to general socioeconomic progress, but inherent limits in human
174 physiology and societal structure are likely to set a bound to the potential for further adaptations in the future. It is
175 thus of paramount importance that strategies aimed at further reducing the mortality burden of forthcoming warmer
176 summers are implemented in parallel with mitigation efforts from governments and the general population to avoid
177 reaching tipping points and critical thresholds in temperature projections.

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Author Contributions

EG and JB conceived the study idea. EG, RFMT and JB collected, pre-processed and validated the underlying data. EG, JB and HA did the statistical analyses, and EG, MQZ and JB wrote the first draft of the manuscript. All authors contributed to subsequent versions, as well as to the interpretation of data and results. All authors reviewed and approved the final version of the manuscript.

Competing Interests Statement

We declare no competing interests.

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Figure 1. Temperature-related mortality risk and incidence.

a, Cumulative relative risk of death for the overall population in the factual period 2015-2019 in the 35 European countries (blue), and in the 23 countries for which data were available since the year 2000 (red). **b**, Cumulative relative risk of death for the overall population in the counterfactual periods 2000-2004 (blue), 2005-2009 (black) and 2010-2014 (red) in the 23 European countries for which data were available since the year 2000. Shadings in **a,b** correspond to the 95% CIs. **c-f**, Regional heat-related mortality rate (deaths per million) aggregated over the year of 2023 for the overall population (**c**), people aged 80+ (**d**), women (**e**) and men (**f**).

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293 **Table 1. European sex- and age-specific heat-related mortality numbers and rates during 2023 for different**
 294 **factual and counterfactual epidemiological associations.**

295 The minimum mortality temperature (°C) and the relative risk of death (unitless) at temperature 95th and 99th
 296 centiles were calculated with data from the periods 2000-2004, 2005-2009, 2010-2014 and 2015-2019 in the 35
 297 European countries, or in the 23 European countries for which data were available since the year 2000. Relative
 298 risks for each period and age and sex group were calculated by centering the exposure-response association at its
 299 respective minimum mortality temperature. These associations were used to calculate the heat-related mortality
 300 number (deaths) and rate (deaths per million) aggregated over 2023. Values in parentheses represent the 95% CIs.
 301 The attributable rate ratio (%) of a period is calculated as its relative difference with 2015-2019; i.e. period minus
 302 2015-2019, divided by 2015-2019.
 303

Population Group	Variable	35 Countries		23 Countries		
		Factual Model	Factual Model	Counterfactual Model		
		2015-2019	2015-2019	2010-2014	2005-2009	2000-2004
Overall	Minimum Mortality Temperature (°C)	18.2	17.7	16.5	16.4	15.0
	Relative Risk at Temperature 95 th Centile	1.14 (1.11, 1.17)	1.11 (1.08, 1.15)	1.09 (1.07, 1.11)	1.09 (1.07, 1.12)	1.07 (1.02, 1.11)
	Relative Risk at Temperature 99 th Centile	1.17 (1.14, 1.21)	1.14 (1.10, 1.18)	1.11 (1.08, 1.13)	1.12 (1.09, 1.16)	1.08 (1.03, 1.14)
	Attributable Number (deaths)	47690 (28853, 66525)	21255 (15704, 25959)	26926 (7228, 46145)	34977 (14909, 53202)	38036 (21305, 54497)
	Attributable Rate (deaths per million)	88 (53, 122)	75 (56, 92)	96 (26, 164)	124 (53, 189)	135 (75, 193)
	Attributable Rate Ratio (%)	---	---	+28.0	+65.3	+80.0
Women	Attributable Rate (deaths per million)	113 (64, 156)	89 (44, 131)	129 (72, 185)	163 (37, 280)	163 (72, 246)
	Attributable Rate Ratio (%)	---	---	+44.9	+83.1	+83.1
Men	Attributable Rate (deaths per million)	73 (48, 98)	57 (22, 90)	68 (43, 90)	96 (-12, 189)	106 (44, 165)
	Attributable Rate Ratio (%)	---	---	+19.3	+68.4	+86.0
Age 0-64	Attributable Rate (deaths per million)	13 (5, 21)	8 (1, 15)	7 (-1, 16)	10 (-18, 37)	13 (3, 21)
	Attributable Rate Ratio (%)	---	---	-12.5	+25.0	+62.5
Age 65-79	Attributable Rate (deaths per million)	127 (15, 238)	112 (-1, 214)	159 (47, 268)	170 (46, 290)	200 (51, 349)
	Attributable Rate Ratio (%)	---	---	+42.0	+51.8	+78.6
Age 80+	Attributable Rate (deaths per million)	1102 (653, 1533)	884 (607, 1155)	1183 (748, 1594)	1772 (889, 2613)	1774 (995, 2444)
	Attributable Rate Ratio (%)	---	---	+33.8	+100.5	+100.7

317 Methods

319 *Data sources*

321 The study used weekly counts of all-cause mortality by sex and age groups from Eurostat²⁹. Missing data were
322 complemented by contacting the corresponding national agencies for statistics. The final dataset included 96,342,990
323 counts of death (47,046,865 for women and 46,780,242 for men) between January 2000 and November 2023. All-age
324 data by sex were not available in the United Kingdom, and only at the country level in Germany. All-sex data by age
325 were not available in Ireland and the United Kingdom, and only at the country level in Germany.

327 We transformed the hourly gridded 2-meter temperature data from the high-resolution ERA5-Land reanalysis³⁰ into
328 weekly regional averages of daily mean 2-meter temperature.

330 *Statistical analysis*

332 For the statistical analysis, we applied the two-stage approach described in Ballester et al.¹⁷, please find references
333 therein. Epidemiological models were fitted separately for each combination of period and sex and age groups.

335 In the first stage, we used quasi-Poisson regression models to calculate the location-specific temperature-lag-
336 mortality relationship in each European region³¹. The models included (1) an intercept, (2) a natural cubic spline of
337 time with 8 d.f. per year to control for the seasonal and long-term trends, and (3) a cross-basis function to estimate
338 the exposure-lag-response association between weekly temperatures (*temp*) and mortality counts (*mort*):

$$339 \log(E(mort)) = intercept + ns(time, 8 \text{ d.f. per year}) + crossbasis(temp; 0, 1, 2, 3 \text{ weeks})$$

340 We modelled the exposure-response function of the cross-basis with a natural cubic spline with three internal knots
341 at the 10th, 50th and 90th percentiles of the location-specific weekly temperature distribution, and the lag-response
342 function of the cross-basis with integer lag values of 0, 1, 2 and 3 weeks.

344 In the second stage, we pooled the location-specific coefficient derived from the first stage using a multivariate,
345 multilevel meta-regression analysis³². The meta-regression included (1) two levels of random effects by regions
346 nested within countries, and the location-specific (2) temperature average, (3) temperature interquartile range and
347 (4) percentage of people aged 80+ years as meta-predictors³³. We calculated the best linear unbiased predictions of
348 the temperature-mortality relationship in each region from the meta-regression³⁴ to (i) obtain the location-specific
349 minimum mortality temperature, which serves as reference to calculate the relative risks at temperature 95th and 99th
350 centiles, and to (ii) transform the regional temperature and mortality time series into temperature-related mortality
351 numbers³⁵. Heat-related mortality was calculated for the weeks with average temperatures above the location-
352 specific minimum mortality temperature. Regional heat-related mortality numbers were aggregated to obtain the
353 national and continental burdens. Similarly, we computed 1,000 Monte Carlo simulations of the regional heat-related
354 mortality numbers, and separately aggregated them in each simulation to calculate the 95% CIs at the national and
355 European levels^{21,33}. We calculated heat-related mortality rates (in deaths per million) by using the yearly regional
356 population estimates from Eurostat³⁶. We only analyzed countries for which mortality data were available, in order
357 to exclusively consider only data-driven relative risks and attributable mortalities.

358 All statistical analyses were performed with R software (version 4.3.2)³⁷ using the packages *splines* (“*ns*” for natural
359 cubic splines), *dlnm* (for the first-stage regression), and *mixmeta* (for the second-stage meta-analysis).

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362 *Factual-counterfactual analysis*

363

364 In the main analyses, the epidemiological models were fitted with data from the period 2015-2019, which were then
365 used to transform the temperature and mortality time series from the year of 2023 into heat-related mortality
366 numbers. These analyses were done for 823 contiguous regions in 35 countries, representing a population of over
367 543 million Europeans, namely Albania (12 regions), Austria (35), Belgium (44), Bulgaria (28), Croatia (1), Cyprus (1),
368 Czechia (14), Denmark (11), Estonia (5), Finland (19), France (96), Germany (16), Greece (52), Hungary (20), Iceland
369 (2), Ireland (1), Italy (103), Latvia (6), Liechtenstein (1), Lithuania (10), Luxembourg (1), Malta (1), Montenegro (1),
370 the Netherlands (40), Norway (11), Poland (73), Portugal (25), Romania (42), Serbia (25), Slovakia (8), Slovenia (1),
371 Spain (59), Sweden (21), Switzerland (26) and the United Kingdom (12).

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373 In a second set of analyses, we considered the 429 regions from the 23 countries for which data were available since
374 the year 2000, representing a population of almost 282 million people, namely Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia,
375 Estonia, Finland, Germany, Hungary, Iceland, Ireland, Latvia, Liechtenstein, Luxembourg, Norway, Poland,
376 Portugal, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland and the United Kingdom. In these countries, we
377 separately fitted the same epidemiological models as in the main analysis, but with data from the periods 2000-2004,
378 2005-2009, 2010-2014 and 2015-2019^{38,39}. Thus, separately for each of the four time periods, we estimated the location-
379 specific temperature-lag-mortality relationship in each European region (first stage), and calculated the best linear
380 unbiased predictions and minimum mortality temperatures (second stage). Finally, we used the association obtained
381 from the fittings to separately transform the temperature and mortality time series from the year of 2023 into heat-
382 related mortality numbers. Please note that we here generically use the word “*adaptation*” to refer to the temporal
383 changes in the exposure-response curves, both including the minimum mortality temperature and relative risks.

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385 *Sensitivity analyses*

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387 We conducted sensitivity analyses by modifying the degrees of freedom per year used to control for the seasonal
388 and long-term trends. We refer to Ballester et al.¹⁷ for the sensitivity of estimates to other parameter choices.

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390 **Ethics declarations**

391 The authors declare no need for ethical approval because they only used publicly available datasets.

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393 **Data Availability Statement**

394 This study is based on publicly available datasets: mortality counts from Eurostat
395 (https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Weekly_death_statistics&stable); temperature
396 values from the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts
397 (<https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/cdsapp#!/dataset/reanalysis-era5-land?tab=overview>); and population numbers
398 from Eurostat (https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/cache/metadata/en/demo_r_gind3_esms.htm).

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400 **Code Availability Statement**

401 The computer code illustrating the analyses is available at https://github.com/Eligallo/Europe_2023_heat_adaptation

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403 **Methods-only references**

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=== Extended Data ===

Extended Data Table 1. National sex-specific heat-related mortality numbers and rates during 2023.
 Values in parentheses represent the 95% CIs. The numbers and rates for women and men do not include the United Kingdom.

Country	Attributable number (deaths)			Attributable rate (deaths per million)		
	Overall	Women	Men	Overall	Women	Men
Albania	363 (129, 573)	194 (49, 332)	86 (12, 159)	120 (43, 190)	129 (33, 221)	57 (8, 105)
Austria	486 (154, 844)	297 (-59, 612)	234 (111, 356)	54 (17, 94)	65 (-13, 134)	53 (25, 80)
Belgium	324 (-46, 706)	186 (-83, 431)	122 (-32, 275)	28 (-4, 61)	32 (-14, 73)	21 (-6, 48)
Bulgaria	1670 (894, 2493)	899 (376, 1325)	724 (341, 1104)	229 (123, 343)	241 (101, 355)	204 (96, 312)
Switzerland	294 (91, 501)	243 (54, 418)	90 (23, 159)	34 (10, 57)	55 (12, 95)	21 (5, 37)
Cyprus	151 (45, 238)	82 (16, 148)	70 (30, 109)	167 (50, 263)	176 (35, 319)	159 (68, 248)
Czechia	361 (2, 736)	355 (59, 615)	57 (-57, 171)	34 (0, 69)	65 (11, 113)	11 (-11, 32)
Germany	6376 (4142, 8521)	3119 (1255, 5266)	2149 (965, 3320)	76 (50, 102)	74 (30, 125)	52 (24, 81)
Denmark	189 (-3, 386)	91 (-71, 246)	39 (-8, 85)	32 (-0, 66)	31 (-24, 83)	13 (-3, 29)
Estonia	103 (14, 186)	74 (7, 140)	19 (-4, 42)	75 (11, 137)	102 (10, 194)	30 (-7, 65)
Greece	4339 (3294, 5340)	2749 (2122, 3310)	1293 (785, 1771)	393 (298, 483)	486 (375, 585)	239 (145, 328)
Spain	8352 (5464, 11373)	5180 (2863, 7195)	3165 (1872, 4443)	175 (114, 238)	212 (117, 295)	135 (80, 189)
Finland	138 (-109, 391)	227 (-84, 520)	13 (-22, 50)	24 (-19, 69)	80 (-30, 182)	5 (-8, 18)
France	2734 (759, 4897)	1334 (-300, 2805)	1586 (682, 2440)	41 (11, 74)	39 (-9, 82)	50 (21, 76)
Croatia	561 (257, 828)	353 (142, 542)	167 (62, 273)	132 (61, 195)	161 (64, 247)	82 (30, 133)
Hungary	294 (-51, 665)	304 (-36, 610)	74 (-91, 249)	29 (-5, 66)	58 (-7, 116)	16 (-19, 52)
Ireland	60 (-172, 265)	68 (-97, 237)	0 (-19, 20)	12 (-34, 52)	27 (-38, 93)	0 (-8, 8)
Iceland	0 (0, 0)	2 (-10, 13)	0 (0, 0)	0 (0, 0)	9 (-53, 71)	0 (0, 0)
Italy	12743 (9451, 16176)	8388 (5683, 10708)	4436 (3364, 5429)	209 (155, 265)	267 (181, 341)	150 (113, 183)
Liechtenstein	1 (-1, 3)	1 (-1, 2)	0 (-0, 0)	19 (-34, 65)	32 (-38, 100)	1 (-17, 18)
Lithuania	247 (65, 437)	89 (4, 160)	124 (49, 195)	83 (22, 147)	56 (2, 101)	90 (36, 142)
Luxembourg	33 (-8, 72)	18 (-3, 40)	4 (-5, 14)	51 (-13, 111)	57 (-8, 125)	14 (-16, 43)
Latvia	58 (-57, 183)	23 (-33, 76)	24 (-15, 61)	29 (-28, 91)	21 (-30, 69)	26 (-16, 66)
Montenegro	41 (-7, 85)	25 (-11, 62)	6 (-7, 19)	66 (-11, 137)	78 (-34, 197)	20 (-22, 61)
Malta	70 (-10, 132)	40 (-12, 89)	39 (11, 66)	134 (-19, 254)	157 (-49, 355)	146 (40, 244)
Netherlands	368 (-47, 806)	260 (-108, 599)	124 (-53, 299)	21 (-3, 46)	29 (-12, 67)	14 (-6, 34)
Norway	29 (-19, 73)	9 (-35, 52)	26 (-11, 62)	5 (-4, 13)	3 (-13, 19)	9 (-4, 23)
Poland	616 (-183, 1460)	457 (-348, 1178)	212 (-51, 460)	16 (-5, 38)	23 (-18, 59)	11 (-3, 25)
Portugal	1432 (965, 1873)	794 (473, 1088)	519 (356, 685)	136 (92, 178)	143 (85, 197)	104 (71, 137)
Romania	2585 (1362, 3832)	1192 (129, 2124)	1384 (839, 1910)	128 (68, 190)	116 (13, 206)	141 (85, 194)
Serbia	464 (227, 699)	380 (134, 588)	205 (60, 349)	66 (32, 99)	105 (37, 163)	60 (18, 101)
Sweden	13 (-46, 80)	20 (-64, 99)	3 (-12, 17)	1 (-4, 8)	4 (-12, 19)	1 (-2, 3)
Slovenia	95 (-19, 193)	61 (-3, 130)	36 (-2, 75)	45 (-9, 92)	58 (-3, 124)	34 (-2, 71)
Slovakia	247 (4, 502)	117 (-40, 257)	83 (11, 158)	45 (1, 90)	41 (-14, 91)	31 (4, 58)
United Kingdom	1851 (501, 3111)	Not Available	Not Available	28 (8, 47)	Not Available	Not Available
Europe	47690 (28853, 66525)	27627 (15662, 37978)	17117 (11146, 22935)	88 (53, 122)	113 (64, 156)	73 (48, 98)

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Extended Data Table 2. National age-specific heat-related mortality numbers and rates during 2023.
Values in parentheses represent the 95% CIs. The numbers and rates do not include Ireland and the United Kingdom.

Country	Attributable number (deaths)			Attributable rate (deaths per million)		
	0-64	65-79	80+	0-64	65-79	80+
Albania	24 (-13, 61)	51 (2, 96)	171 (66, 267)	9 (-5, 23)	144 (6, 271)	1964 (755, 3070)
Austria	60 (-20, 138)	184 (45, 323)	252 (-14, 528)	8 (-3, 19)	149 (37, 260)	482 (-26, 1008)
Belgium	67 (-31, 164)	59 (-232, 340)	257 (-47, 574)	7 (-3, 17)	37 (-143, 209)	389 (-72, 868)
Bulgaria	146 (-111, 386)	600 (219, 963)	939 (399, 1467)	25 (-19, 66)	508 (185, 816)	2734 (1160, 4269)
Switzerland	42 (-62, 143)	68 (-119, 251)	221 (-49, 499)	6 (-9, 20)	57 (-100, 211)	467 (-103, 1056)
Cyprus	13 (-6, 32)	22 (-6, 47)	114 (38, 174)	17 (-8, 43)	192 (-50, 417)	3191 (1075, 4877)
Czechia	20 (-55, 98)	64 (-59, 187)	295 (37, 561)	2 (-6, 11)	37 (-35, 109)	653 (82, 1242)
Germany	506 (106, 907)	971 (296, 1692)	3678 (1395, 5687)	8 (2, 14)	77 (24, 135)	602 (228, 930)
Denmark	39 (6, 70)	60 (-80, 198)	50 (-46, 152)	8 (1, 15)	66 (-88, 219)	170 (-159, 523)
Estonia	17 (-7, 43)	19 (-5, 42)	42 (-18, 106)	15 (-7, 39)	96 (-26, 218)	519 (-227, 1326)
Greece	246 (18, 434)	526 (113, 923)	3051 (2048, 4027)	28 (2, 50)	315 (67, 552)	3902 (2619, 5149)
Spain	806 (211, 1349)	1172 (269, 2061)	6650 (4310, 8820)	21 (5, 35)	176 (41, 310)	2257 (1463, 2993)
Finland	13 (-19, 45)	44 (-48, 136)	60 (-86, 215)	3 (-4, 10)	47 (-50, 144)	182 (-260, 649)
France	781 (131, 1366)	1295 (-326, 2815)	1484 (-33, 3112)	15 (2, 26)	131 (-33, 284)	362 (-8, 759)
Croatia	28 (-24, 81)	126 (25, 223)	330 (128, 507)	8 (-7, 23)	191 (39, 339)	1473 (571, 2261)
Hungary	10 (-22, 42)	156 (-47, 359)	258 (-13, 533)	1 (-3, 5)	101 (-30, 232)	576 (-29, 1192)
Ireland	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available
Iceland	5 (-23, 30)	2 (-22, 24)	0 (0, 0)	16 (-71, 94)	51 (-517, 559)	0 (0, 0)
Italy	756 (98, 1318)	1747 (785, 2710)	10102 (7001, 13220)	16 (2, 28)	181 (81, 281)	2235 (1549, 2925)
Liechtenstein	0 (-0, 0)	0 (-0, 1)	0 (-1, 2)	3 (-6, 12)	25 (-60, 106)	205 (-620, 909)
Lithuania	54 (-12, 123)	50 (-7, 107)	137 (8, 270)	22 (-5, 51)	121 (-18, 261)	827 (46, 1628)
Luxembourg	5 (-1, 10)	5 (-6, 15)	11 (-11, 31)	8 (-1, 18)	68 (-86, 221)	447 (-417, 1206)
Latvia	7 (-19, 34)	5 (-23, 33)	82 (-9, 176)	5 (-12, 21)	18 (-78, 115)	723 (-79, 1540)
Montenegro	4 (-6, 14)	9 (-7, 25)	19 (-6, 41)	7 (-11, 26)	119 (-83, 312)	921 (-287, 1963)
Malta	11 (-1, 22)	15 (-11, 39)	40 (-8, 78)	27 (-1, 52)	192 (-144, 499)	1761 (-356, 3462)
Netherlands	131 (11, 245)	133 (-317, 550)	242 (-100, 598)	9 (1, 17)	50 (-118, 205)	283 (-117, 699)
Norway	187 (-121, 454)	47 (-74, 159)	2 (-5, 8)	42 (-27, 101)	62 (-98, 212)	7 (-20, 33)
Poland	249 (5, 461)	63 (-156, 289)	412 (-185, 1051)	8 (0, 14)	11 (-28, 52)	243 (-109, 620)
Portugal	161 (48, 272)	241 (55, 421)	906 (518, 1294)	19 (6, 33)	138 (32, 241)	1258 (719, 1797)
Romania	485 (34, 911)	849 (222, 1476)	1213 (381, 2076)	29 (2, 54)	296 (77, 514)	1301 (408, 2227)
Serbia	95 (30, 164)	247 (89, 407)	136 (-38, 326)	17 (5, 29)	216 (78, 356)	417 (-116, 1003)
Sweden	16 (-24, 59)	41 (-107, 187)	6 (-37, 54)	2 (-3, 7)	26 (-69, 120)	11 (-65, 96)
Slovenia	6 (-11, 23)	22 (-10, 53)	59 (-8, 121)	3 (-7, 13)	67 (-30, 161)	505 (-65, 1028)
Slovakia	25 (-30, 81)	60 (-47, 168)	94 (-20, 215)	5 (-6, 17)	78 (-62, 221)	493 (-108, 1127)
United Kingdom	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available	Not Available
Europe	5016 (1796, 7962)	8951 (1043, 16748)	31313 (18565, 43549)	13 (5, 21)	127 (15, 238)	1102 (653, 1533)

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Extended Data Figure 1. Weekly temperature and heat-related mortality numbers in Europe during the summers of 2023 and 2022.

a,b Weekly baseline (gray line) and observed (black line) temperature (°C) averaged over Europe during the summers of 2023 (**a**) and 2022 (**b**). Temperature anomalies are defined as the difference between observed and baseline temperatures (gray shading). Baseline temperatures were computed as the mean annual cycle of observed temperatures in 1991-2020. **c-f** Weekly heat-related mortality (weekly deaths) aggregated over Europe during the summers of 2023 (**c,e**) and 2022 (**d,f**) for the overall population (black in **c,d**), women (red in **c,d**), men (blue in **c,d**) and people aged 0-64 (blue in **e,f**), 65-79 (red in **e,f**) and 80+ (black in **e,f**) years, together with their 95% CIs (shadings). The numbers for women and men do not include the United Kingdom; values for the age groups do not include Ireland and the United Kingdom. The x-axis shows weeks 22-39 of years 2023 and 2022.